

Discriminating Factors of Internal Informal Cordial Relationship: University vs. Bank

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Abstract:

Workplace relationship can be built up very easily by frequent interaction with faithful, loyal and trustworthy colleagues. It becomes solid, good and rewarding relationships both for the organization and employees. The service-oriented organizations try to maintain and introduce standard policy to make the employees loyal. Due to job nature and frank engagement with colleagues, a variety of factors have been influenced to make the relationship among the employees. The exact happening and to make out the critical factors differentiating the relationship are the prime concern of this study. With the light of the technicalities affected through psychological and other common characteristics, the authors aim to identify the set discrimination function based on the random selection of employees which is in total 200 in numbers with a semi-structured questionnaire from two different dimensional organizations like university and bank under service industry. By using the tools-SPSS 22.0 with the help of discriminant analysis, significant mean differences were observed for all the predictors on category of these two different dimensional organizations. The discriminant function revealed significant association between groups and all predictors, accounting for 89.18% of between group variability although the closer outlook under structure Matrix shown only four key predictors, namely organization retention policy (0.647), job satisfaction & security (0.879), teamwork (0.582), and close intimacy (0.280). Again, the cross-validated classification showed that overall 85.0% cases were correctly classified. The generalization of those attributes might become convincing and favorable elements to build up a smooth work environment in an organization.

Key terms: Cordial Relationship; Employee Relations; Discriminant Analysis.

Introduction

Social satisfaction in the workplace had the most powerful influence on productivity, group interaction, and good leadership by satisfying personal relations in workplace. It is also being considered as a key determinant of job satisfaction (Mayo, 1945). For loyalty, the organization depends not only on need satisfaction of employees but also related to organizational commitment (Steers, 1977), job satisfaction, intention to switch (Zinovieva, Ten Horn, & Roe, 1993), achievement, recognition for accomplishment, increased responsibility and opportunities for growth and development (Herzberg, Mausner, & Snyderman, 2011). This kind of relationship among coworkers had little bit of more influence compared to the amount which had focused on leaders and supervisors. (Raabe & Beehr, 2003). Informal relationships in organizations stay within the realm of both social and organizational psychology. This is really a wholehearted psychological attachment found in employee settings what can't see in the professional world, but may present in family bindings/settings (Lozada, 1996).

Organization itself is not a container for relationships but it is an integral part of relationship in the organization and plays a key part in its development process (Sias, & Cahill, 1988). The relationship occurs between individuals assuming to be similar to themselves, usually with respect to attitudes, values and interest (Anderson & Hunsaker, 1985). In addition, they may perform similar work, in similar occupations, probably with a similar educational background (Sias & Cahill, 1998). Moreover, people working toward the common goal can increase positive feelings toward same team members. Based on performance, pleasant working environment is more rewarding than an unpleasant one (Anderson & Hunsaker, 1985). To reduce workplace envy, one of the ways is to create "strong team player" adhering to the informal, unofficial workplace "rules" (Bedeian, 1995).

Literature Review

Several organizational researchers in the past decade have been contributing to the literature in the area of workplace friendship both theoretically and empirically, but little research on coworkers' influences at work had done comparing to the amount which has emphasized on supervisors and leaders (Raabe & Beehr, 2003). This is really a wholehearted psychological attachment found in employee settings what can't see in the professional world (Lozada, 1996). Interpersonal informal relationship in an organization can change the rules of motivation and loyalty factors. According to Plato, true friendship is derived from basic human needs and desires, such as wanting to strive toward goodness, to love and be loved, and to seek self-understanding (Blieszner & Adams, 1992). Basically, informal relationships in organizations stay within the realm of both social and organizational psychology. The base line for satisfaction of the employees in an organization is related to productivity and efficiency in the workplace (Mayo, 1945). But, this is absolutely a belongingness/ interactional setting where employees/colleagues connected with psychological bindings (Markiewicz, Devine, & Kausilas, 2000). In university, the colleagues maintain friendly relations in between and continue. This is an absolute emotional settings/illusion where one can't think of separation and the switching rate is comparatively too low for this kind of relationship (Levy, 2003). This bondage made the employees attached and spent time in between.

Women's organizational relationships were characterized by greater intimacy than those of men that reflects findings in non-work contexts (Fritz, 1997). On the other hand, men's workplace relationships were characterized by more mutual dependence and it involved more activities that women's; also reflecting from non-work contexts (Wright, & Scanlon, 1991). So, the salient features worked behind their relationship or friendship were proximity, similarity, working towards a common goal, social exchange and intrinsic rewards (Fine, 1986). In relationship, information peers are less open, and use less functional communication skills, than either collegial or special peers. That's why; peer relationship differs in context to closeness, strength, multiplicity and communication (Myers, Knox, Pawlowski, & Ropog, 1991). Again, peer relationships at workplace are considered to be one of the primary means by which organizational socialization takes place (Louis, Posner, & Powell, 1983).

Organizational commitment is considered to be an important factor for creating affective response to the whole organization whereas satisfaction of job influences the job's specific aspects, but both of them contribute individually to the intention of leave of employees in an organization (William & Hazer, 1986). Again, job satisfaction and organizational commitment correlated positively (Fisher, 2002).

The psychological climate and cohesion were related to collegial and special peer relationships (Odden & Sias, 1997). The effects of interpersonal relationships under a "team orientation dimensions" and a "respect for people dimension" have had an influential role on retention (Sheridan, 1992). It is also found from the studies that if the coworkers have relatively less autonomy, they have a proportionately greater need for solidarity with their peers (Fine, 1986). High pressure work environment is opposed to such kind of relationship and develop less cohesive and negative attitude among coworkers which ultimately result in higher turnover. In some cases, informal relationship in some cases arouses intention to leave due to presence of negative relationships (Dillard & Fritz, 1995).

Furthermore, interpersonal-relationships exert influence a variety of performance and attitudinal outcomes (Riordan & Griffeth, 1995). The supervisory support is one of the significant factors of job satisfaction (Gaertner, 1999) which made relationship either by the level of trust between subordinate and supervisors (Cunningham & MacGregor, 2000), by the extent to which supervisors and subordinates like and respect each other (Murphy & Ensher, 1999) or, by the way tasks are assigned by the supervisors (Blau, 1999). However, trust leads to a higher level of loyalty (Hunt, & Morgan, 1995) by favorable and positive intentions toward the welfare and interests of the object (Ballester and Aleman, 1999).

Both men and women were found to derive more emotional support and therapeutic value from their relationships (Winstead, 1995). Generally, both males and females report more instrumental & emotional rewards, and greater satisfaction from relationship (Markiewicz, Devine, & Kausilas, 2000; Veniegas & Peplau, 1997). The most research attention has been done those of superior-subordinate in workplace relationships (Vecchio & Bullis, 2001). The role of status and power are very salient in many workplaces, because work roles are usually prescribed by the organization with clearly defined status hierarchies. That's why; the role of organizational influence cannot be avoided. Virtually all close relationships involve shared interests and activities, intimacy, emotional support, small talk and the exchange of tangible favors, regardless of the gender of the participants (Wright, & Scanlon, 1991).

Methodology

The study is descriptive in nature conducted by using a survey method. Here, internal informal cordial relationship is a categorical variable consisting of two major categories/options: University and Bank. Like all other factors, the most considerable factors for making the cordial relationship are relaxation in workload, similar educational background, common goal, career development and training facilities, flexibility, proximity, opportunity for involving personal task, organization retention policy; job satisfaction & security, independence & autonomy, sharing of feelings, teamwork, participatory decision making, close intimacy and sacrifice.

Based on the significant attributes, questionnaire has been set. But in data screening, all factors are not significantly discriminate between these two different dimensional organizations. That's why; the attributes for analysis are revised and the most significant attributes are close intimacy, independence & autonomy, job satisfaction & security, organization retention policy; and teamwork. Along with demographic questions in a format of open-ended questions, independent variable (relationship factors) are attributes based where the attributes are rated on importance scale highly important (5) to not all important (1) whereas categories prevailed as university and bank for dependent variables. The survey was addressed to the faculties and staffs serving at private universities such as, University of Information Technology & Sciences (UITS), Port City University, Feni University, BGMEA Institute of Fashion and Technology, Southern University at Chittagong, and private commercial banks like Dutch Bangla Bank Limited, NCC Bank Limited, Fast Security Islamic Bank Limited, Social Islami Bank Limited, & One Bank Limited. In total 250 employees were randomly selected from the sample organizations where response rate was 80% i.e, 200 respondents. Being included into the cluster of having different types of preferences made by employees/samples, discriminant analysis is an appropriate technique to classify the cases with categorical dependent variables and metric independent variables and to explore significant relationship (Malhotra & Dash, 2010). From the philosophical consideration, this is a 'quantitative positivist' approach under epistemological and ontological paradigm (Bhattacharjee, 2012).

The typical Discriminant function is:

$$D = a + W_1X_{1k} + W_2X_{2k} + W_3X_{3k} + \dots + W_kX_{nk}$$

Where,

D = Discriminant score

a = Intercept

W_1 = Discriminant Weight for Independent Variables 'i'(importance of each X in helping us distinguish the attributes making the cordial relationship)

X_{ik} = Independent variables for object 'k'

Usually the sample has been split into analysis sample and holdout sample for cross validation. In this study, the analysis sample was 60% i.e. 120 cases, 60 cases for each group and holdout samples for remaining 80 cases, 40 cases for each group.

Result

The SPSS 22.0 has been used to analyze the data according to the specification required for discriminant analysis. However, the Discriminant model validity is justified through the significance of discriminant functions and re-classifying the cases. One of the relative importance available in discriminate analysis is to develop predictive model for generalization of other samples (Hair, Black, Babin, Anderson, & Tatham, 2006).

Table # 1(a) : Group Statistics

Cordial Relationship		Mean	Std. Deviation	Valid N (listwise)	
				Unweighted	Weighted
Univer sity	Independence & Autonomy	2.5226	.83100	60	60
	Job Satisfaction & Security	3.8426	.59585	60	60
	Organization Retention Policy	3.8142	.71028	60	60
	Teamwork	3.1291	.90655	60	60
	Close Intimacy	3.7128	.69380	60	60
Bank	Independence & Autonomy	2.5935	.86464	60	60
	Job Satisfaction & Security	3.7490	.60386	60	60
	Organization Retention Policy	3.6700	.79042	60	60
	Teamwork	3.0020	.73383	60	60
	Close Intimacy	3.3482	.80114	60	60
Total	Independence & Autonomy	2.5589	.84827	120	120
	Job Satisfaction & Security	3.7946	.60117	120	120

Organization Retention Policy	3.7403	.75509	120	120
Teamwork	3.0640	.82417	120	120
Close Intimacy	3.5259	.77182	120	120

Table # 1(b) : Tests of Equality of Group Means

	Wilks' Lambda	F	df1	df2	Sig.
Independence & Autonomy	.998	13.431	1	118	.001
Job Satisfaction & Security	.994	4.930	1	118	.032
Organization Retention Policy	.991	4.420	1	118	.036
Teamwork	.994	4.873	1	118	.037
Close Intimacy	.944	28.402	1	118	.000

Group membership can be predicted on significant difference between groups on each of the independent variables using group means and ANOVA result data. Here in the Group Statistics Table (#1a) , it has been seen the strong evidence of significant differences between means of university and bank for all independent variables like close intimacy, independence & autonomy, job satisfaction & security, organization retention policy; and teamwork and also found very high value of F's in table# 1(b) .

Table # 2: Pooled Within-Groups Matrices^a

	Independence & Autonomy	Job Satisfaction & Security	Organization Retention Policy	Teamwork	Close Intimacy
Correlation Independence & Autonomy	1.000	.224	.359	.423	.008
Job Satisfaction & Security	.224	1.000	.531	.402	.021
Organization Retention Policy	.359	.531	1.000	.566	.022
Teamwork	.423	.402	.566	1.000	.051
Close Intimacy	.008	.021	.022	.051	1.000

a. The covariance matrix has 118 degrees of freedom.

Again, the Pooled – Within Group Matrices (table # 2) also supports use of these independent variables being low in inter-correlation

Table # 3: Eigenvalues.

Function	Eigenvalue	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Canonical Correlation
1	2.377 ^a	100.0	100.0	.837

a. First 1 canonical discriminant functions were used in the analysis.

The minimum number of Discriminant functions is the minimum of either the number of independent variables or less than one category of dependents variables (Hair et.al, 2006). Here only one function is displayed due to considering two groups namely university and bank in table # 3. The canonical correlation is the multiple correlations between the predictors and the discriminant function. So, a canonical correlation of 0.837 suggests the model explaining 70.05% (R^2) of the variation in the grouping variables whether a cordial relationship exists in either university or bank.

Table # 4: Wilks' Lambda

Test of Function(s)	Wilks' Lambda	Chi-square	df	Sig.
1	.929	35.232	5	.000

Here in table # 4: Wilks' Lambda Values exerted the significance of the function. The chi-square statistics is also supporting to the Wilks' Lambda for statistical significance means to have a relation between dependent groups and independent variables.

Table # 5: Standardized Canonical Discriminant Function Coefficients

	Function
	1
Independence & Autonomy	-.365
Job Satisfaction & Security	.618
Organization Retention Policy	.698
Teamwork	.573
Close Intimacy	.564

The Standard Canonical Discriminant Function Coefficients provides the index of each predictor where sign indicates the direction of relationship. Organization retention policy was the strongest predictor while job satisfaction & security, teamwork, and close intimacy were next in importance as predictors in table # 5. Independence & autonomy was less successful as predictor.

Table # 6: Structure Matrix

	Function
	1
Job Satisfaction & Security	.879
Organization Retention Policy	.647
Teamwork	.582
Close Intimacy	.280
Independence & Autonomy	-.151

Pooled within-groups correlations between discriminating variables and standardized canonical discriminant functions

Variables ordered by absolute size of correlation within function.

In table # 6, the structure matrix indicates the relative importance of the predictors and correlations means to shows the correlation of each variable with each discriminate function i.e. discriminant loadings. Usually the cut-off value between important and less important variables is 0.30 like factor analysis loadings, here independence & autonomy and close intimacy are not clearly loaded on the discriminant functions means to weakest predictors and suggests that these attributes are not differentiating the relationship factors between university and bank, but a function of other un-assessed factors.

Table # 7: Canonical Discriminant Function Coefficients

	Function
	1
Independence & Autonomy	-.230
Job Satisfaction & Security	.497
Organization Retention Policy	.596
Teamwork	.411
Close Intimacy	.251
(Constant)	-.832

Unstandardized coefficients

The Un-standardized Canonical Discriminant Function Coefficients are used to create the discriminant function equation which provides relative importance of each of the predictor in table # 7. In this case, the discriminant function is-

$$D = (0.596 \times \text{Organization Retention Policy}) - (0.230 \times \text{Independence \& Autonomy}) + (0.411 \times \text{Teamwork}) + (0.251 \times \text{Close Intimacy}) + (0.497 \times \text{Job Satisfaction \& Security}) - 0.832$$

Table # 8: Functions at Group Centroids

Cordial Relationship	Function
	1
University	.283
Bank	-.283

Unstandardized canonical discriminant functions evaluated at group means

Group Centroid describes each group in terms of its profile using group means (Centroid) of the predictor variables and it is discriminatory as well as per the table value (table#8).

Table # 9(a): Classification Results^{a,c}

Cordial Relationship			Predicted Group Membership		Total
			University	Bank	
Original	Count	University	110	10	120
		Bank	16	104	120
	%	University	91.67	8.33	100.0
		Bank	13.3	86.7	100.0
Cross-validated ^b	Count	University	108	12	120
		Bank	24	96	120
	%	University	90.0	10.0	100.0
		Bank	20.0	80.0	100.0

a. 89.18% of original grouped cases correctly classified.

b. Cross validation is done only for those cases in the analysis. In cross validation, each case is classified by the functions derived from all cases other than that case.

c. 85.0% of cross-validated grouped cases correctly classified.

**Table # 9(b): Classification Results^{a,c} for cases not selected for use in the analysis
(Holdout Sample)**

Predictors			Predicted Group Membership		Total
			University	Bank	
Original	Count	University	36	4	40
		Bank	3	37	40
	%	University	90	10	100
		Bank	7.5	92.5	100
Cross-validated ^b	Count	University	34	6	40
		Bank	4	36	40
	%	University	85	15	100
		Bank	10	90	100

a. 91.25% of original grouped cases correctly classified.

b. Cross validation is done only for those cases in the analysis. In cross validation, each case is classified by the functions derived from all cases other than that case.

c. 87.5% of cross-validated grouped cases correctly classified.

The classification result reveals that 89.18% of respondents were correctly classified in between groups (Hit ratio) in table # 9(a). The respondents opined that university (91.67%) is classified with slightly better chances of building up relationship than those of banks (86.7%) which is larger than the chance ratio (50/50 for equal size group). Most researchers accepted a hit ratio of more than 25% due to chance and here 85.0% of cross-validated grouped cases correctly classified. Again, in table # 9(b), the classification result for cases not selected for use in the analysis (holdout sample) is 87.5 % of cross-validated grouped cases correctly classified. Finally, the discrimination function has got worthiness of prediction on building up the relationship by considering relevant attributes.

Discussion

The earlier research conducted on employee attitudes aggregated at the company level (Denison, 1990), and the bank branch level (Ryan, Schmit, & Johnson, 1996) based on relation to other organizational outcomes such as financials and employee turnover. So, the relationship that compare between the university and the bank are worthy and logically evidential. The development of causal model on the discriminating points also added vast contribution on literature in this field. The employees of bank basically were in a pressure from customer service and related functions which may be absent in the university. The university employees functionally got relaxation in workplace comparing to bank employee. But the self responsibility grows much in university level whereas financial risk is much more in bank. The type and level of work make these two organizations distinctive. This distinction also affects the level of employee relationship as well. Consequently, the predictors those are very influential in employee relationship in university somewhat different nature in bank. The result of this study has implications not only on discriminating the construct of internal cordial relationships but also on identifying the level of relationship based on practice. Organization retention policy of banks and university are different because in private banks, the

amount paid for salary is comparatively higher than university employees. That's why the satisfaction of banks for financial perspective is somewhat preferential than on university but the liberty and freedom are far better in university than on bank. Consequently, the relative effect of organization retention policy, satisfaction and teamwork are made combined effort on making the cordial relationship in the organization. Participatory decision making in an organization can be worked on the decision of higher authority and it is some cases related to teamwork. But team members' opinions are considered based on the expertise and skills. So, both of university and banks have intimacy and cooperation that's why these two are not differentiating very particularly but these factors have a clear influence on relationship buildup.

This research study was conducted to find the possible key differentiators on building up internal informal cordial relationship between university and bank. Research indicates that organization retention policy, job satisfaction & security, and teamwork are strong predictors for the relationship, and independence & autonomy and participatory decision making are poor predictors. These results are consistent with existing literature highlighting the role of retention strategies and job security in fostering employee loyalty and commitment. In particular, the relatively high discriminant loadings of job satisfaction and security (0.879) and retention policy (0.647) indicate that organizational practices that ensure stability and career progression significantly contribute to the quality of workplace relationships. Likewise, teamwork (0.582) and close intimacy (0.280) demonstrate the importance of interpersonal engagement and social bonds in strengthening collaboration and mutual trust.

Additionally, the high classification accuracy (85%) suggests that the selected predictors provide a reliable framework for understanding how workplace relationships can be systematically distinguished across service industries. However, it also raises critical implications: while organizational policies play a decisive role, psychological and interpersonal aspects are equally important in sustaining long-term employee engagement. This study thus bridges both organizational and individual-level perspectives in analyzing workplace dynamics. Nevertheless, limitations must be acknowledged. The sample was restricted to only two types of service organizations, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other sectors. Moreover, reliance on self-reported data through semi-structured questionnaires may introduce subjectivity. Future studies could adopt longitudinal approaches and include a broader range of organizations to validate the discriminant function more comprehensively.

Conclusions

This study concludes that effective workplace relationships are not merely the result of frequent interactions but are largely shaped by a combination of organizational policies and interpersonal factors. Specifically, retention policies, job satisfaction and security, teamwork, and close intimacy emerged as key determinants in fostering loyalty, trust, and collaboration among employees. By correctly classifying 85% of cases, the discriminant model demonstrated a strong capacity to differentiate relational dynamics between universities and banks, thereby offering valuable insights for organizational development. For managers and policymakers in service-oriented organizations, the implications are clear: investing in employee retention strategies, ensuring job security, promoting teamwork, and encouraging healthy interpersonal relationships are crucial for building a rewarding and stable work environment.

By prioritizing these factors, organizations can enhance both employee well-being and organizational performance. Further research can be conducted on business level outcomes for each of the organization by measuring employee satisfaction and turnover depending on constituents identified. The best opportunity for such research might play roles for setting and creating best working practices in the organization. So, the physical condition and the culture of the organization are considerable issues for future growth and development of the organization. If it is possible to maintain a healthy environment throughout the organization, the relationships will positively induce the satisfaction and loyalty of the organization.

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